

Clinical Trial Report

Safety evaluation of the DiaSole insole with
diabetic foot ulcers

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Who We Are

In 2021 the Trittech Institute was launched. We are a team based in a bespoke facility within Hywel Dda University Health Board comprising of industry-leading engineers, scientists and clinicians.

Our Institute

Here at the TriTech Institute, we support the development of healthcare solutions on a local, national, and global level offering designers and manufacturers a single point of access to the NHS through a collaborative and agile approach.

What We Offer

The team's advanced skills in clinical and research design are combined with technical engineering expertise to manage the whole innovative pathway from early unmet need, through to concept design, prototyping, clinical investigations, and real-world service evaluations.

Our Services

We provide specific services and solutions for clinical engineering, research and innovation and Value-Based healthcare and can also support with grant writing and submission.

Executive Summary

Background

Neuropathy and ischaemia are two pathologies that develop in the feet of individuals who have diabetes type 1 or 2, both of which lead to foot ulceration. Peripheral nerves in the lower limbs are susceptible to different types of damage in individuals who have diabetes, due to hyperglycaemia (Edmonds et al., 2021).

Up to approximately 34% of people with type 1 or 2 diabetes develop a diabetic foot ulcer (DFU) in their lifetime, about 20% of these will undergo a lower extremity amputation (LEA) to remove the foot as a result of infection and progressive gangrene (Armstrong et al., 2023). A further 20% of people with DFU require hospitalisation, of which 15% to 20% will also require LEA (Armstrong et al., 2023).

The International Working Group on the Diabetic Foot (IWGDF) recommend that a non-removable knee-high offloading device with an appropriate foot-device interface is the first choice of offloading treatment to promote the healing of ulcers (Munro et al., 2021).

Felted foam and prescription footwear with foot orthoses insoles can also be considered if no other options are possible with the patient, but they are currently not recommended for healing stages of ulceration due to a lack of evidence of the effectiveness (Munro et al., 2021). Orthotic insoles are currently recommended for preventing recurrence of DFUs, and there is evidence to suggest that orthotics can prevent primary ulceration (Munro et al., 2021).

Evaluation overview

TriTech was commissioned by Kaydiar LTD. on 18/08/2022 to carry out a clinical investigation of DiaSole, which was setup as an 'Extended Phase 2 Product Evaluation Single Sample Study'. This clinical trial began patient recruitment on the 30/06/2023 and concluded on the 30/09/2024.

The principal research question was to assess the safety of the DiaSole insole with patients who have neuropathy of the feet caused by diabetes type 2, and who either have superficial ulcers or at risk of an ulcer developing. In order to assess this principal research question, unexpected adverse events (AE) were to be recorded throughout the trial period.

The secondary research questions for this clinical trial were:

- For those that have a superficial pressure ulcer, does the pressure ulcer heal or reduce in size whilst using the DiaSole insole?
- Is the DiaSole insole acceptable to the clinicians and patients?

Methodology

The trial aimed to recruit a minimum of 33 adult participants with a diagnosis of type 1 or type 2 diabetes and who also have an indication of pressure ulcer/lesion with a designation of 0A or 1A on the Texas wound classification scale (Armstrong et al., 1998).

Participants who potentially fulfilled the inclusion criteria for the trial had their eligibility confirmed by an appropriately delegated member of the research team with access to and a full understanding of the potential participant's medical history.

Baseline assessments took place after informed consent was obtained (visit 0) in the trial process. This was completed alongside any relevant standard of care treatment performed by the clinical team before the CI could issue the DiaSole insole.

Study participants were reviewed at regular set intervals. These intervals were weekly follow ups for the first 4 weeks, then a final assessment at week 8. Follow-up assessment windows had a permissible +/- 2-day variance to give flexibility to clinical staff and reduce disruption to the participants. Feedback was also collected from participants and clinicians where possible at week 8.

Results

Only 5 participants of the required 33 reached the screening stages for the trial. 1 of these participants were not issued with the DiaSole following exclusion during the eligibility screening. Of the 4 participants who were successfully recruited into the trial, 2 had a positive outcome indicating a reduction in ulcer/lesion size and positive feedback from the participants. The other 2 participants were withdrawn from the trial due to new blister or skin formations that were deemed to be a risk for continued use, however the cause of this may not have been solely from the use of DiaSole so no unexpected AEs were reported as a result.

Discussion

Due to the difficulties with participant recruitment throughout the trial, a number of significant and non-significant amendments were made and subsequently approved by the MHRA, REC/HCRW bodies. These amendments included expanding the eligibility criteria, extensions to the trial end date on two occasions and the inclusion of modified insole dimensions in response to 7 eligible participants not being recruited due to issues with the DiaSole fitting into footwear.

Research clinicians also fed back that they would be able to recruit participants in larger numbers if this could be used for patients who had not yet formed an ulcer or lesion at all but were at risk as a means to prevent this entirely.

Feedback from research clinicians indicated that a large majority of the participants that were being screened and who were being considered for screening had Texas grade 0A ulcers or lesions that had already healed. The intended focus from the commercial sponsor, Kaydiar, was for ulcer healing purposes.

The research clinicians had previously provided feedback on the cascade of options available to them clinically, where TCCs and air cast offloading boots are clinically proven to be most effective with patients who have Texas grade 1A or more severe ulcers and lesions. This is in line with the podiatry consensus document for offloading (Munro et al., 2021).

Conclusion

Due to the ongoing difficulties with participant recruitment it has not been possible to come to any meaningful conclusions about the safety and effectiveness of the DiaSole insoles. Feedback from HDUHB podiatrists involved in this trial indicated that the DiaSole could have more use in future as a means of completely preventing ulcer or lesion develop in those at risk of diabetic foot ulcers, instead of a means for healing them. However this was not the intention of the funding from the commercial sponsor.

Recommendation 1: Wider stakeholder engagement with podiatry

The feedback from HDUHB podiatry did not agree with feedback obtained prior to this trial. A wider stakeholder engagement exercise to conform the value proposition and intended patient population will help to guide more suitable patient selection criteria for future DiaSole trials.

Recommendation 2: Explore preventative use of the DiaSole insole

HDUHB podiatry feedback indicated that the DiaSole would have more value as a means to completely prevent ulcers or lesions forming for those at risk of diabetic foot ulcers. This would require a different trial methodology, likely requiring a longer follow up period comparing the likelihood of developing of a diabetic foot ulcer between those using DiaSole and those on other standard issue insoles and with no insole.

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Abbreviations

AE	Adverse Event
CI	Chief Investigator
CRF	Case Report Form
DFU	Diabetic Foot Ulcer
GCP	Good Clinical Practice
HDUHB	Hywel Dda University Health Board
HCRW	Health and Care Research Wales
HRA	Health Research Authority
ICF	Informed Consent Form
IG	Information Governance
IWGDF	International Working Group on the Diabetic Foot
KD	Kinneir Dufort
LEA	Lower Extremity Amputation
MDFT	Multidisciplinary footcare team
MHRA	Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency
MTPJs	Metatarsophalangeal joints
PIS	Patient Information Sheet
REC	Regional Ethics Committee
SAE	Serious Adverse Event
TCC	Total Contact Cast

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We would like to thank Mike Mulroy as the clinical lead and Chief Investigator (CI) for this evaluation, and the entire podiatry team who participated in this clinical investigation on behalf of Hywel Dda University Health Board.

We would like to thank Michael Clark as a co-investigator from the Welsh Wound Innovation Centre and the support offered during the setup of the clinical investigation.

We would also like to thank the commercial sponsors David Barton and Heather Smart for providing training and expertise for the DiaSole to clinical staff and ConvaTec for funding this clinical investigation.

1. Background

1.1. Diabetic foot ulcers

Diabetes is a complex metabolic disorder which can be characterised by hyperglycaemia, which results in an abnormal and continuously raised blood glucose level (Banday et al., 2020). The presentation and pathogenesis of diabetes varies between individual, but hyperglycaemia will lead to dysfunctions in multiple organs, and it will negatively affect the vasculature of the individual affected (Banday et al., 2020).

Type 1 diabetes constitutes roughly 5-10% of all known cases and is an autoimmune disorder which results in insulin deficiency and ultimately hyperglycaemia. Type 1 diabetes can occur in individuals of any age (Banday et al., 2020). Type 2 diabetes is characterised by insulin resistance, and which progresses very slowly often asymptotically, and constitutes 90-95% of all known cases. Diabetes type 2 typically affects older adults and be caused by genetic and environmental factors (Banday et al., 2020).

Neuropathy and ischaemia are two pathologies that develop in the feet of individuals who have diabetes type 1 or 2, both of which lead to foot ulceration. Peripheral nerves in the lower limbs are susceptible to different types of damage in individuals who have diabetes, due to hyperglycaemia (Edmonds et al., 2021).

Peripheral arterial disease is the most important factor in the development of the Diabetic foot ulcer (DFU), and severe ischemia of the skin of the lower extremities leads to ulcerated tissues becoming necrotic due to insufficient blood supply (Deng et al., 2023). Foot ulceration caused by neuropathy and ischaemia can also be complicated by infection (Edmonds et al., 2021).

Up to approximately 34% of people with type 1 or 2 diabetes develop a DFU in their lifetime, about 20% of these will undergo a lower extremity amputation (LEA) to remove the foot as a result of infection and progressive gangrene (Armstrong et al., 2023). A further 20% of people with DFU require hospitalisation, of which 15% to 20% will also require LEA (Armstrong et al., 2023).

1.2. Management of DFU by podiatry

A multidisciplinary footcare team (MDFT) is required for the successful management of DFU which include podiatrists, nurses, orthotists, and physicians (Edmonds et al., 2021). The ultimate aim of diabetic foot care is to avoid DFU and the resulting LEAs, where the role of the podiatrist includes educational strategies and foot care strategies with the patient (Blanchette et al., 2020).

The term 'offloading' is widely used when describing methods for supporting the healing of DFUs. Offloading can be done utilising load redistribution or load sharing so that weight bearing surfaces are changed so that plantar pressures are reduced, which in turn can reduce the force applied to the areas of the foot that are prone to or have a DFU (Munro et al., 2021).

The International Working Group on the Diabetic Foot (IWGDF) recommend that a non-removable knee-high offloading device with an appropriate foot-device interface is the first choice of offloading treatment to promote the healing of ulcers (Munro et al., 2021). The total contact cast (TCC) and modified non-removable casts both provide load redistribution and load sharing properties (Munro et al., 2021).

Previous studies show that the TCC is viewed as the most effective method for treating DFUs, but patient compliance for this level of offloading is low, meaning podiatrists often need to consider other options (Fife et al, 2014). The application of the TCC is documented as being inconsistent, with only 35% of plantar ulcers in Europe being treated by one. The reasons for this inconsistency include service and clinician factors such as staff training and knowledge and patient factors and expectation management (Munro et al., 2021).

Other options that can be considered for offloading if a TCC is not used include air-cast boots, heel/hindfoot relief shoes and bespoke ankle-height modified casts (Munro et al., 2021). Felted foam and prescription footwear with foot orthoses insoles can also be considered if no other options are possible with the patient, but they are currently not recommended for healing stages of ulceration due to a lack of evidence of the effectiveness (Munro et al., 2021). Orthotic insoles are currently recommended for preventing recurrence of DFUs, and there is evidence to suggest that orthotics can prevent primary ulceration (Munro et al., 2021).

1.3. DiaSole Insole

DiaSole is an insole developed by Kaydiar LTD. to aid the treatment of DFUs through offloading of plantar pressure. DiaSole is modular in construction, allowing cells of the insole to be removed or added depending on the location of the patient's foot ulcer. The removal of cells creates a direct offloading cavity, reducing pressure on that area of the foot. Figure 1 shows a diagram of the cell removal for DiaSole (Kaydiar, 2023).

1.4. Previous evaluations with DiaSole

Prior evaluations relating to the DiaSole are detailed below, no adverse events had been reported to date in this work.

Phase 1 Product Evaluation

The phase 1 study sought to test the effectiveness of the DiaSole insole to offload specific areas of the foot. Data was collected over a four to six-week period for 10 participants with type 2 diabetes, without foot ulceration. Foot plantar pressure data was recorded and assessed using the RS Scan 2-meter gait plate. The 10 participants found the DiaSole insole to be comfortable and easy to fit by the research podiatrist. There were no reports of slippage or irritation when worn during the gait cycle.

Results of the phase 1 product evaluation were:

- Average of 36% pressure reduction at the 1st MTPJ when using the DiaSole insole with an offload cavity at the 1st MTPJ vs no insole
- Average of 42% pressure reduction at the plantar heel when using the DiaSole insole with an offload cavity at the plantar heel vs no insole

- These results exceed the 30% pressure reduction that has been recommended by the International Working Group on the Diabetic Foot (IWGDF) for the management of DFUs (Schaper et al., 2020).

Phase 2 Product Evaluation

The phase 2 study involved a mixture of 10 healthy participants and 4 participants who had type 2 diabetes without active ulceration, but who were at risk of re-ulceration. All participants in this phase 2 evaluation were asked to wear the insole for a four-week period.

Results of the phase 2 product evaluation were:

- Reduction in pain
- Reduced callus formation
- One reported limitation was around the fitting and this related to the volume of the insole inside of the toe box when placing within shallower footwear. While this has been encountered in some cases, the majority have so far demonstrated positive results when worn in sensible footwear.
- The product appeared to be well-tolerated with all participants reporting a high score in ease of wear, and it appears from the compliance scores that continued acceptance of the product is likely.
- The in-use feedback positive from the participants. All participants so far have found the product easy to clean and are reporting the device is showing little or no signs of wear or tear.

Figure 1 shows the DiaSole cell removal instructions, taken from the instructions for use document (Kaydiar, 2023).

2. Clinical trial overview

TriTech was commissioned by Kaydiar LTD. on 18/08/2022 to carry out a clinical investigation of DiaSole, which was setup as an 'Extended Phase 2 Product Evaluation Single Sample Study'. This clinical trial began patient recruitment on the 30/06/2023 and concluded on the 30/09/2024.

2.1. Trial details

Appropriate governance processes were followed before the clinical trial officially began in June 2023. These processes included regional ethics committee (REC) review and subsequent Health Research Authority (HRA) and Health and Care Research Wales (HCRW) approval, approval was also required and granted by the Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency (MHRA). Local HDUHB Information Governance (IG) processes were also followed through the trial period.

Study Title: Safety evaluation of the DiaSole insole with diabetic foot ulcers

Acronym/Short Title: DiaSole: Safety evaluation of the DiaSole insole with diabetic foot ulcers

Study ID (IRAS No.): 322107

REC Reference: 22/WA/0342

MHRA Reference: CI/2023/0012/GB

2.2. Trial aims

Primary research question

The principal research question was to assess the safety of the DiaSole insole with patients who have neuropathy of the feet caused by diabetes type 2, and who either have superficial ulcers or at risk of an ulcer developing.

In order to assess this principal research question, adverse events (AE) were to be recorded throughout the trial period.

An AE is any untoward medical occurrence in a clinical trial subject who has been administered an intervention and which does not necessarily have a causal relationship with said treatment. An adverse device event (ADE) includes all untoward and unintended responses to a medical device. All AEs and ADEs were to be recorded during this trial. The podiatrists/research clinicians monitored the participants during the follow up appointments to monitor for anything that might constitute an AE.

AEs that were to be reported related to:

- A. Occurrence of new foot ulceration
- B. Evidence of skin irritation or soreness on the foot
- C. Progression in size or inflammation or infection of the off-loaded ulcer
- D. Tripping and falls

Secondary research questions

The secondary research questions for this clinical trial were:

- For those that have a superficial pressure ulcer, does the pressure ulcer heal or reduce in size whilst using the DiaSole insole?
- Is the DiaSole insole acceptable to the clinicians and patients?

2.3. Outcome measures

Primary outcomes

- a) Number of adverse events related to diabetic foot ulceration and its care, including occurrence of new foot ulceration; evidence of skin irritation or soreness on the foot; progression in size or inflammation or infection of the off-loaded ulcer/lesion; tripping and falls.

Note – Due to the nature of the pathology of diabetic foot ulcers and the patient population being recruited, it was anticipated that some expected AEs could occur as they do with standard insoles and treatments. Any AE that was deemed unexpected or specifically a fault or cause for concern of the DiaSole insole were to be counted for the primary outcome

Secondary outcomes

- a) Number of all AEs reported during study
- b) Change in ulcer/lesion area in (mm²) (length in mm x width in mm) from baseline to week 8.
- c) Change in ulcer/lesion depth (mm) where appropriate from baseline to week 8, recorded using disposable measuring tape and sterile probe
- d) Device ease of use
- e) Product hygiene information (if the insole required washing)
- f) Product wear and tear

2.4. Service context

Location

Hywel Dda University Health Board (H DUHB) is one of seven local Health Boards in Wales. It provides primary and secondary care services for residents within its borders in the counties of Carmarthenshire, Pembrokeshire, and Ceredigion. Prince Philip hospital (PPH) has an onsite dedicated Clinical Research Centre (CRC) with facilities including a patient waiting area and a clinical consultation room. The podiatry department within H DUHB includes many hospital and community-based clinics across the three counties of Hywel Dda.

Researcher team

Chief Investigator (CI): Mike Mulroy, head of podiatry, H DUHB

Other Investigators: Billy Woods, Hywel Dda University Health Board (H DUHB) and Michael Clark, Welsh Wound Innovation Centre.

Research Clinicians: Included podiatrists, whose specialities are in diabetes and research nurses within local sites.

2.5. Patient Screening

The trial aimed to recruit a minimum of 33 adult participants with a diagnosis of type 1 or type 2 diabetes and who also have an indication of pressure ulcer/lesion with a designation

of 0A or 1A on the Texas wound classification scale (Armstrong et al., 1998). See Appendix 1 for the Texas wound classification scale.

- Grade 0A (Texas) – Pre- or post-ulcerative lesion completely epithelialised.
- Grade 1A (Texas) – Superficial wound not involving tendon, capsule, or bone.

Eligibility Criteria

The inclusion criteria can be seen below:

Inclusion Criteria

1. Age 18 years and above.
2. Patient able and willing to give written informed consent.
3. UK Shoe size 3-11.
4. Diagnosis of Diabetes type 1 or 2.
5. Active foot ulceration (plantar aspect), Grade 1A and/or at risk of ulceration or re-ulceration/lesion, Grade 0A (based on the University of Texas wound grading system) with signs of increased pressure or breakdown at the site (extravasation or erythema). Appropriate footwear (which has room to safely accommodate the DiaSole insole).
6. Patient is appropriate for standard offloading insole as part of their standard treatment.

Exclusion Criteria

1. More than one ulcer/lesion on the same foot.
2. History of or active Charcot foot or severe foot deformity.
3. Amputation of at least one foot.
4. Critical limb ischemia.
5. Sensory neuropathy of the upper limbs/hands.
6. Visual impairment (cannot see feet and footwear properly).
7. History of drug and alcohol abuse.
8. Have known contraindications to the materials used in the product insoles. Allergies to cotton or silicone.
9. Patients who are non-concordant and do not have appropriate footwear that could house the DiaSole insole.
10. Unable to attend regular hospital visits – e.g., housebound.
11. Are currently enrolled in any other research.
12. Individuals who do not already have access to a language translator when one is required for understanding of the English language.

Note - The research clinicians were expected to use their experience and clinical judgement when issuing the insole to participants with foot deformity during the course of the study.

2.6. Participant recruitment and informed consent

Potentially eligible patients were identified from regular screening of podiatry clinics (See Appendix 2 for patient pathway from the National Plantar Ulceration Off Loading Pathway document). Clinicians were to carry out periodic searches of their patient lists to identify

eligible patients and invite those patients to take part in the trial by letter, email, telephone, or in-person at the patient's next appointment.

Participants who potentially fulfilled the inclusion criteria for the trial had their eligibility confirmed by an appropriately delegated member of the research team with access to and a full understanding of the potential participant's medical history. If eligibility was assessed and documented, then the process of obtaining informed consent was delegated as appropriate and documented on the DiaSole Site Delegation Log.

It was the responsibility of the CI to obtain written informed consent for each participant prior to performing any trial related procedures. Consent could also be taken by other podiatrists (with up-to-date Good Clinical Practice (GCP) training) as delegated by the research team and recorded on the DiaSole Site Delegation Log. Research nurses and other allied health professionals could also obtain consent if local practice allowed and this responsibility had been delegated by the CI and again, captured on the DiaSole Site Delegation Log.

3. Methodology

The sequence of events for the trial participants can be seen in Appendix 4, the detail surrounding these trial events can be seen in the following sections.

3.1. Baseline assessment

The baseline assessments took place after informed consent was obtained (visit 0) in the trial process. Baseline information was collected by the research clinician and included the following:

- Confirmation that eligibility criteria has been met.
- Confirmation of informed consent including date consented.
- Participant details: Date of Birth, sex, weight, UK shoe size.
- Diabetes information:
 - Type 1 or Type 2
 - Insulin controlled or non-insulin controlled.
 - Details of last HbA1c result (Date, mmol/mol).
- Current medication in relation to:
 - Anticoagulant medication.
 - Immunosuppressant medication.
- Details of participants feet, to include where relevant:
 - Current ulcer/lesion location.
 - Previous history of ulcer/lesions on this foot.
 - Texas grade.
 - Duration of Ulcer/Lesion.
 - Ulcer/lesion measurement (Length, Width, Depth (If applicable) recorded using disposable clinical tape measures and a sterile probe following standard of care treatment of foot/feet (e.g., scalpel debridement) by treating clinical team).

- Erythema measurement (Length, Width, recorded using disposable clinical tape measures and a sterile probe following standard of care treatment of foot/feet (e.g., scalpel debridement) by treating clinical team) if present.
- Sensory examination of feet (Monofilament across 3 areas, date of last examination, only needs to be on the day if last examination was >12 months ago).
- Vascular examination of feet (Dorsal/posterior hand palpable and doppler signal recorded, monophasic, biphasic, triphasic or none, only needs to be on the day if last examination was >12 months ago).
- Edinburgh Claudication Questionnaire (positive or negative for claudication pain).
- Pre-Issue Pathway likelihood for onward referral (Vascular, Orthopaedic, General Inpatient) to be scored on a Likert Scale.
- Visual assessment of patients' feet (taking note of any deformities or restricted motion).
- Assessment of patients' footwear (Noting toe box depth, width, secure fastenings, inserts), to ensure they are suitable for offloading insoles.

The baseline visit assessment, as listed above, was completed alongside any relevant standard of care treatment (e.g., debridement and redressing of wounds) performed by the clinical team, before the CI (or suitably qualified research team member) could issue the DiaSole insole. DiaSole insoles were fitted and dispensed at baseline visit or within 5 days of baseline visit completion where reasonably practical.

At the end of the baseline visit, the trial participants were informed that if they experienced any pain, discomfort, irritation, difficulty walking or if they noticed any deterioration in their condition, including clinical signs of infection that they should access healthcare as they would normally, as outlined in the patient information sheet (PIS), and at the earliest available opportunity to notify the research team. Details of who to contact was included in the PIS and the participant diary. See Appendix 3 for the PIS that was issued to potential participants of the trial.

During the trial the DiaSole insole was fitted into the participant's own footwear. The research clinician checked the participant's footwear once the insole was in situ to ensure that there was no bulging in the toe box area that would indicate a fitting issue.

The participant was required to wear the insole within footwear that has been reviewed and approved by the research clinician, for the total duration of the trial period whenever the participant was weight-bearing. This was made clear to the participant both verbally by the research clinician and highlighted in the PIS.

3.2. Follow up assessments

Study participants were reviewed by an appropriate member of the research team on the DiaSole delegation log, at regular set intervals. These intervals were weekly follow ups for the first 4 weeks, then a final assessment at week 8. Day 0 being the day of DiaSole insole fitting

and dispensing. Follow-up assessment windows had a permissible +/- 2-day variance to give flexibility to clinical staff and reduce disruption to the participants.

In order to reduce disruption to the participants and their usual care given the research team minimised any deviation from the usual national plantar ulceration off-loading patient pathway (Appendix 2). If an in-person ulcer/lesion assessment was not required as part of standard of care treatment the study protocol allowed for assessment to be conducted using real-time telemedicine or remote video consultation at weeks 1, 2 and 3. Follow-up assessments at weeks 4 and 8 required face-to-face appointments with participants.

The follow-up assessments for weeks 1, 2, 3, 4, and 8 all included:

- Patient status.
- Changes in medication.
- Assessment of participants feet and DiaSole insole use, including:
 - Pain.
 - Discomfort.
 - Rubbing or irritation.
 - Difficulty walking.
 - Changes to ulcer/lesion.
 - Signs of infection or allergic reaction.
 - Incidences of trips or falls.
- Use of any healthcare services.

Additional at **weeks 4 and 8** the face-to-face assessments also included:

- Ulcer/lesion location.
- Texas grade of ulcer.
- Ulcer/Lesion measurements (Length x Width and Depth).
- Erythema measurement (Length x Width) if applicable.

The following additional information was also collected during the final assessment, **week 8**:

- Return and assessment of DiaSole insoles.
- Status of the participants ulcer/lesion.
- Completion of End of Trial Review Feedback Questionnaire (Patient).
- Research podiatrist assessment of the DiaSole insole.

3.3. Data collection and analysis

With participants consent, anonymised copies of any medical photographs of the participants ulcer(s)/lesion(s) were to be sent to the research team for analysis. Photographs were to be labelled with the participants unique study ID, date taken and which foot e.g., left foot, right foot.

‘Before DiaSole insole’ photographs were to be taken within 1 week of participants’ baseline trial visit and ‘after DiaSole insole’ photographs were to be taken within +/- 1 week of the participants final study visit (week 8), with participants’ consent.

Case report forms (CRFs) were used to document all study visits and capture any AEs or ADEs. The CRF were completed by delegated research clinicians. If an AE or ADE was not defined as SERIOUS, then the event were to be reported in line with local HDUHB procedures and recorded in the local investigator site file, and the participant were to be followed up by the research team. Any AE or ADE were to be documented in the participants' medical notes (where appropriate) and on the CRF. Serious adverse events (SAEs) were to be documented by the CI or delegated study personnel using a DiaSole SAE form and be reported to the MHRA.

The main analysis of data was to be conducted on changes from baseline to week 8 outcome measures. The trial aimed to recruit 33 participants for analysis, based on power calculations conducted by a statistician under the employ of Kaydiar LTD. This power calculation was based on secondary outcomes as they were unable to power in relation to safety calculations at the time.

It was anticipated that the reduction in ulcer area from baseline of matched pairs would be of a medium effect; represented by a standardised difference (ratio of difference in means to standard deviation of paired differences) of 0.5. 33 participants, assessed at baseline and post-intervention, would be required to be able to reject the null hypothesis that this response difference is zero with probability (power) 0.8. The Type I error probability associated with this test of this null hypothesis is 0.05. Therefore, the study needed to recruit a minimum of 33 adult participants with a diagnosis of type 1 or type 2 diabetes and a diabetic foot ulceration/pressure lesion on the plantar aspect of the foot.

Patient feedback

During the week 8 follow up appointment, the participants were asked for feedback using a questionnaire which contained the following questions and statements:

1. Where did you use the insole as part of your offloading care? (Answered by frequency from 'never' to 'as often as I could')
 - a. At home relaxing (watching TV, eating dinner etc.)
 - b. At home whilst doing activities (washing up, cleaning, hoovering etc.)
 - c. Walking whilst outside the house
 - d. Any activity that involved sport (tennis, football etc.)
 - e. At work (Office/Desk based)
 - f. At work (Physical role such as builder, plumber etc.)
2. The DiaSole insole was easy to get into and out of my footwear (Likert response from 'Strongly Agree' to 'Strongly Disagree')
3. The DiaSole instructions for use were easy to follow (Likert response from 'Strongly Agree' to 'Strongly Disagree')
4. The DiaSole device labels were clear and easy to understand (Likert response from 'Strongly Agree' to 'Strongly Disagree')
5. Were there any reasons why you did not wear the insoles as much as you would have liked?
6. Have you had other ulcers on your feet before?
 - a. If yes, were you prescribed any other treatment for this? (Insoles, cast boot?)

- b. If you answered yes to 6, could you give some details of your experience with previous treatments
7. Could you please describe your experience with the DiaSole insole during this trial?
8. Do you have any final comments about the DiaSole insole?

Clinician feedback

During the week 8 follow up appointment, the attending research clinician was asked for feedback using the following question on the CRF:

1. It was easy to remove cells from the DiaSole insole to create the offloading space. (Likert response from 'Strongly Agree' to 'Strongly Disagree')
2. It was easy to create an offloading space on the DiaSole insole that corresponded with the ulcer/lesion area (Likert response from 'Strongly Agree' to 'Strongly Disagree')
3. The DiaSole insole fit well into the patients' shoe with no issues to report (Likert response from 'Strongly Agree' to 'Strongly Disagree')
4. The participant used the DiaSole insole as intended (Likert response from 'Strongly Agree' to 'Strongly Disagree')

Research clinicians were also asked for additional feedback for the DiaSole insole and its use during the trial, as free text on the CRF.

4. Results

This trial required 33 participants for analysis of secondary outcome measures, however only 5 participants were consented into the trial after confirmation of eligibility criteria. Due to this the results sections that follow contain information from the patient screening log to highlight issues faced with recruitment. The 5 participants that were recruited are included here as case studies.

4.1. Patient screening

The HDUHB research team kept a research participant screening log of all patients that were considered by research clinicians as being potentially eligible. The screening log was used to document these potential participants, including those that were recruited after eligibility checks and consenting. The log also included all patients that were deemed unsuitable after eligibility checks and information as to why they were unsuitable.

Between the dates of 12/07/2023 and 09/09/2024 a total of 25 patients were screened, of these:

- 5 were subsequently enrolled onto the DiaSole trial
- 1 declined after being provided with additional information
- 11 were excluded using the eligibility criteria:
 - 2 had infections of the foot (who were subsequently not eligible once the infections had cleared).
 - 1 had a Charcot foot deformity.
 - 1 had osteomyelitis.
 - 1 had severe arterial disease.

- 1 had no signs of sensory neuropathy (this eligibility criteria was later changed to aid recruitment, see discussion section).
- 3 had ulcers too high on the Texas scale (>1A), or that had become more severe and required TCC or other more suitable offloading solutions.
- 2 were deemed ineligible with no additional clinical notes.
- 1 patient was also issued crutches changes the weight bearing nature of the foot requiring offloading.
- 7 had footwear that would not house the DiaSole effectively and were unable to participate, despite meeting all other eligibility criteria.

4.2. Case studies for recruited patients

4.2.1. HD_001

Patient demographics and baseline assessment (06/09/2023)

- Male, 75 years old.
- Diabetes type 2.
- Foot size: UK size 9 Male
- Lesion details:
 - Right foot.
 - <6 months old.
 - Length = 20mm, Width = 20mm, Depth = 0mm.
- Foot assessment: Cvoid style feet, prominent metatarsophalangeal joints (MTPJs), but the foot flattened when weight bearing. Some redness and pressure across all MTPJs. Recently healed ulcer
- Texas grade of ulcer: 0A.
- DiaSole issued had no cells removed.
- No medical photography images available.

Follow up at week 1 (13/09/2023)

The week 1 follow up was conducted over the telephone, participant initially reported rubbing on top of the toes for their affected foot (right) but this problem was resolved. Participant reported wearing the DiaSole daily and had not reported any issues or concerns that constituted an AE, ADE, or SAE. Participant was advised to contact clinical staff within podiatry if redness or soreness returned.

Follow up at week 2 (20/09/2023)

Week 2 follow up was conducted over the telephone. Participant reported wearing the DiaSole daily and had not reported any issues or concerns that constituted an AE, ADE, or SAE. Participant also reported that he had been checking the fit of the DiaSole daily and was happy with its use as part of his care.

Follow up at week 3 (27/09/2023)

Week 3 follow up was conducted over the telephone. Participant reported that redness on top of toes in the right foot had returned after increased walking that week. Participant also reported that the ulcer area had become smaller, but this needed confirmation in the week 4

face-to-face appointment. No reported any issues or concerns that constituted an AE, ADE, or SAE.

Follow up at week 4 (04/10/2023)

The week 4 follow up was conducted in person within a clinical environment. Research clinician checked the participants feet, slight red area on top of the 5th toes of both feet but not deemed a concern or adverse event so the DiaSole was not removed. Participant was advised to monitor this redness and self-refer to podiatry if the redness became worse.

Follow up at week 8 (01/11/2023)

The final follow up at week 8 was conducted in person within a clinical environment. No further changes to the feet were reported on this follow up and the DiaSole insoles were returned to the research team. No adverse events reported at this stage.

The ulcer dimensions at week 8 on the right foot P1 MTPJ was: 07.mm length, 10mm width and 0mm depth.

Initial ulcer surface area: 20mm x 20mm = 400mm²

Week 8 ulcer surface area: 0.7mm x 10mm = 7mm²

Total reduction of ulcer surface area = 98.3%

Research clinician noted that the lesion changed from "soft pliable, small delicate" area with poor tissue "primer", to a structured lesion with well-formed epithelium + more calloused supportive structure which was definitely an improvement.

Participant feedback

The feedback from participant HD_001 can be seen in table 1.

Question	Answer
1. Where did you use the insole as part of your offloading care? (Answered by frequency from 'never' to 'as often as I could')	
a. At home relaxing (watching TV, eating dinner etc.)	Sometimes
b. At home whilst doing activities (washing up, cleaning, hoovering etc.)	Sometimes
c. Walking whilst outside the house	As often as I could
d. Any activity that involved sport (tennis, football etc.)	N/A
e. At work (Office/Desk based)	N/A
f. At work (Physical role such as builder, plumber etc.)	As often as I could
2. The DiaSole insole was easy to get into and out of my footwear	Strongly agree

3. The DiaSole instructions for use were easy to follow	Strongly agree
4. The DiaSole device labels were clear and easy to understand	Agree
5. Were there any reasons why you did not wear the insoles as much as you would have liked?	No
6. Have you had other ulcers on your feet before?	No
a. If yes, were you prescribed any other treatment for this? (Insoles, cast boot?)	N/A
b. If you answered yes to 6, could you give some details of your experience with previous treatments	N/A
7. Could you please describe your experience with the DiaSole insole during this trial?	Very good and comfortable.
8. Do you have any final comments about the DiaSole insole?	Better than any insoles I've had before.

Table 1 shows the feedback obtained at the week 8 follow up for participant HD_001.

4.2.2. HD_002

Patient demographics and baseline assessment (25/09/2023)

- Male, 83 years old.
- Diabetes type 1.
- Foot size: UK size 7 Male
- Lesion details:
 - Right foot.
 - <1 months old.
 - Healed ulcer at 3rd MTPJ, with no dimensions measured.
- Foot assessment: Right 3rd plantar MTPJ mild callus over ulcer site.
- Texas grade of ulcer: 0A.
- The DiaSole had 3 cells removed for offloading on the right foot.
- No medical photography images available.

Follow up at week 1 (02/10/2023)

The week 1 follow up was conducted over the telephone, where participant reported that he had experienced pain with other insoles, but not with the DiaSole. Participant also reported that they had a history with falls but feel they were more stable whilst using the DiaSole insoles. No adverse events reported.

Follow up at week 2 (09/10/2023)

Follow up for week 2 was conducted over the telephone. Participant reported that skin had peeled off on the 4th toe of the right foot, but they were not concerned. No blistering reported, but clinical team informed by research clinician. The skin peeling was not considered an adverse event at this time.

Follow up at week 3 (16/10/2023)

The week 3 follow up was conducted over the telephone. Following the report of skin peeling the previous week, the podiatry team arranged for an in-person appointment that took place on the 11/10/2023, but the podiatrist was happy for the participant to continue using DiaSole following this appointment as there was no concern. The skin peeling was not considered an adverse event.

Follow up at week 4 (23/10/2023)

The week 4 follow up was conducted face-to-face in a clinical environment. The skin peeling was again noted, and during this follow up the erythema of the healed ulcer area had been measured as 11mm in length, and 4mm width at the widest point (no measurable depth). Participant instructed to keep using DiaSole as intended for the remaining 4 weeks. No reported incidences or concerns that would indicate AE, ADE, or SAE.

Follow up at week 8 (20/11/2023)

The final follow up at week 8 was conducted in person within a clinical environment. Participant reported occasional pain near planter aspect of foot near the lesion and skin rubbing on top of 5th toe of the right foot whilst using the DiaSole insoles. Research clinician noted that a new callous was forming on the 4th toe on the right foot which was of concern. There was concern with the top layer of the lining of the DiaSole slipping across the insole causing a suspected shearing affect which could have contributed to the new callous formation, this was deemed an expected AE because of the nature of the pathology and was not deemed a specific safety concern of the DiaSole insole at that time. Due to this concern the final assessment included a note of recommending a different insole for this participant after the DiaSole insoles were returned.

The ulcer dimensions at week on the right foot 3rd MTPJ was: 5mm length, 2mm width and 0mm depth.

Initial ulcer surface area: 11mm x 4mm = 44mm²

Week 8 ulcer surface area: 5mm x 2mm = 10mm²

Total reduction of ulcer surface area = 77.3%

The affected right foot was noted to have an improved appearance at week 8 of the trial.

Participant feedback

The feedback from participant HD_002 can be seen in table 2.

Question	Answer
1. Where did you use the insole as part of your offloading care? (Answered by frequency from 'never' to 'as often as I could')	
a. At home relaxing (watching TV, eating dinner etc.)	As often as I could

b. At home whilst doing activities (washing up, cleaning, hoovering etc.)	As often as I could
c. Walking whilst outside the house	As often as I could
d. Any activity that involved sport (tennis, football etc.)	N/A
e. At work (Office/Desk based)	N/A
f. At work (Physical role such as builder, plumber etc.)	As often as I could
2. The DiaSole insole was easy to get into and out of my footwear	Strongly agree
3. The DiaSole instructions for use were easy to follow	Neither agree nor disagree
4. The DiaSole device labels were clear and easy to understand	Disagree
5. Were there any reasons why you did not wear the insoles as much as you would have liked?	No
6. Have you had other ulcers on your feet before?	Yes
a. If yes, were you prescribed any other treatment for this? (Insoles, cast boot?)	No
b. If you answered yes to 6, could you give some details of your experience with previous treatments	N/A
7. Could you please describe your experience with the DiaSole insole during this trial?	Good, comfy
8. Do you have any final comments about the DiaSole insole?	I will miss them

Table 2 shows the feedback obtained at the week 8 follow up for participant HD_002.

4.2.3. HD_003

Patient demographics and baseline assessment (25/09/2023)

- Male, 64 years old.
- Diabetes type 2.
- Foot size: UK size 10 Male
- Lesion details:
 - Left foot.
 - <3 months old.
 - Lesion at 1st MTPJ, with no dimensions measured.
- Foot assessment: Left foot had limited range of motion over 1st toe.
- Texas grade of ulcer: 0A.
- The DiaSole had 8 cells removed for offloading on the left foot, to allow space to add wing additions to the 1st MPTJ are of the left foot.
- No medical photography images available.

Follow up at week 1 (02/10/2023)

The week 1 follow up was conducted via telephone, where participant reported that the DiaSole insoles were comfortable. No issues or concerns were reported by participant or research clinicians. No adverse events to report.

Follow up at week 2 (09/10/2023)

Week 2 follow up was conducted via telephone, and participant reported new blister and skin breakdown on the 1st plantar MTPJ on the left foot. This was logged as an expected AE on the CRF. Additionally some heat and redness was also reported by the participant for both feet after using the DiaSole insoles throughout the day. The research clinician also noted that the participant was seen in clinic by a podiatrist on the 06/10/2023, where the podiatrist had also noted the new blister and had recorded this on the participants medical notes and informed the research team. This new lesion was dressed accordingly by the podiatrist on the 06/10/2023, and at this time the podiatrist advised the participant to cease use of the DiaSole temporarily until the new lesion had begun healing.

Follow up at week 3 (16/10/2023)

Participant was due to see a podiatrist on the 13/10/2023, where the DiaSole insoles and suitability for continued use were to be discussed. However no podiatrists who had GCP training and who were on the trial delegation log were available that day. The participant received their usual care but had to be withdrawn from the trial as the DiaSole insoles could not be re-introduced as per trial protocol.

The participant consented to have their clinical notes checked up to the end of week 8 as per the trial protocol, but further details are not included in this report as these notes did not provide any additional learning for the effect of DiaSole on this participant. The participant had noted that the insoles were comfortable when consulted at weeks 1 and 2, no further feedback was available.

4.2.4. HD_004

Participant 004 was considered for the DiaSole trial but during the screening process in clinic on the 18/10/2023 the participant had sensation in both feet. At the time of screening having sensation in both feet was an exclusion criteria so this participant was withdrawn from the trial.

4.2.5. HD_005

Patient demographics and baseline assessment (25/09/2023)

- Male, 51 years old.
- Diabetes type 2.
- Foot size: UK size 10 Male
- Lesion details:
 - Left foot.
 - <6 months old.
 - Lesion at 3rd MTPJ, measuring 12mm length, 8mm width and 2mm deep.
- Foot assessment: Heavy callus and some extravasation present on the left foot.
- Texas grade of ulcer: 1A

- The DiaSole had 2 cells removed for offloading, on the left foot.
- No medical photography images available

Follow up at week 1 (04/06/2024)

The follow up at week 1 was conducted over the telephone, where participant stated that he had a long-standing injury to his left leg that causes him pain when walking. Participant reported no swelling, redness, or inflammation in either feet after using the DiaSole for a week. No concerns or issues that would constitute an AE.

Follow up at week 2 (12/06/2024)

Follow up at week 2 was conducted face-to-face in a clinical environment, this was due to feedback from the participant indicating the DiaSole insoles were “drawing his feet in”, meaning that his feet were feeling squashed inside the shoe. This feedback from the participant was sent to the clinical and research teams, prompting the in-person visit at week 2. On inspection by the research clinician on 12/06/2024 it was noted that additional heavy callus formation had occurred at the 1A ulcer site on the left foot.

The podiatrist deemed the best course of action clinically at this point was to switch the participant to 5mm Poron red insoles as they were tolerated much better. The DiaSole insoles were returned during this follow and the participant was removed from the trial. The participant did not consent to further data capture from clinical notes, so no further information is available.

Participant feedback

This participant did complete a feedback form, the results of this can be seen in table 3.

Question	Answer
1. Where did you use the insole as part of your offloading care? (Answered by frequency from ‘never’ to ‘as often as I could’)	
a. At home relaxing (watching TV, eating dinner etc.)	Blank
b. At home whilst doing activities (washing up, cleaning, hoovering etc.)	Blank
c. Walking whilst outside the house	Blank
d. Any activity that involved sport (tennis, football etc.)	Blank
e. At work (Office/Desk based)	Blank
f. At work (Physical role such as builder, plumber etc.)	Blank
2. The DiaSole insole was easy to get into and out of my footwear	Strongly disagree
3. The DiaSole instructions for use were easy to follow	Strongly disagree

4. The DiaSole device labels were clear and easy to understand	Strongly disagree
5. Were there any reasons why you did not wear the insoles as much as you would have liked?	Insoles were 'drawing' my feet + causing pain. This is also the case with other bespoke insoles
6. Have you had other ulcers on your feet before?	Yes
a. If yes, were you prescribed any other treatment for this? (Insoles, cast boot?)	Blank
b. If you answered yes to 6, could you give some details of your experience with previous treatments	Blank
7. Could you please describe your experience with the DiaSole insole during this trial?	Insoles are good, fit well but like many of the insoles I have had causing 'drawing' and pain in feet.
8. Do you have any final comments about the DiaSole insole?	Sorry that I could not continue, feels better in just basic cushion insoles.

Table 3 shows the feedback obtained at the week 8 follow up for participant HD_005.

4.3. Clinician Feedback

4.3.1. Feedback from CRFs

As per the trial protocol, the research clinician in attendance of the week 8 follow up with participants were asked 4 questions in relation to the DiaSole and its ease of use. This feedback was answered on 2 occasions and can be seen in table 4.

Question	Response from clinician attending HD_001	Response from clinician attending HD_002
1) It was easy to remove cells from the DiaSole insole to create the offloading space.	Agree	N/A
2) It was easy to create an offloading space on the DiaSole insole that corresponded with the ulcer/lesion area	N/A	N/A
3) The DiaSole insole fit well into the patients' shoe with no issues to report	Strongly agree	Agree
4) The participant used the DiaSole insole as intended	Strongly agree	Agree

Table 4 shows the feedback obtained from research clinicians attending week 8 follow ups for participants HD_001 and HD_002.

Two additional points were raised by the research clinicians that provided feedback. The first of these was that the insoles did not degrade at all during the 8 weeks of use (HD_001). The second additional feedback was concerns with the outer layer of the DiaSole introducing suspected shearing forces by slipping on the silicone main body of the DiaSole (HD_002).

4.3.2. Three counties podiatry feedback

Kaydiar LTD. had previously commissioned Kinneir Dufort (KD) to conduct stakeholder engagement with podiatrists to understand the value proposition in research. An abbreviated version of this document was sent to the TriTech Institute on request following discussions regarding difficulties with participant recruitment. This document (KD, 2022) contained feedback from 6 podiatrists that were from the UK and Germany, who see patients with diabetic foot ulcers daily.

One page of the report stated that 4 out of 6 podiatrists would use DiaSole for prevention of diabetic ulcers and 5 out of 6 would use it for ulcer healing (KD, 2022). A different page of this report stated that 4/6 podiatrists would use the DiaSole for prevention and 2/6 would use it for healing (KD, 2022). This document also stated that of the 6 podiatrists who provided feedback, they would on average be able to use the DiaSole with 59% of patients.

In an effort to obtain more data in relation to the difficulties in participant recruitment, feedback was obtained from a three counties HDUHB podiatry meeting on the 18/12/2023. A web-based tool (Menti Meter) was used to allow podiatrists to answer questions live on-screen during a discussion session.

The questions included in this feedback session included training for use on the DiaSole and whether those in attendance still needed to complete GCP training to be added on to the trial delegation log. But two questions that were asked in response to previous feedback to date at that time were:

- What kind of wounds would you use the DiaSole with?
- Could you estimate the percentage of patients you see that you would want to issue the DiaSole insole to?

These questions were asked to the wider podiatry team (n=31 in attendance), because of information supplied by Kaydiar LTD. (KD, 2022).

Figure 2 shows the results of the question regarding wounds and figure 3 shows the result of the question regarding estimated patient usage.

For the results in figure 3 the podiatrists in attendance at the discussion were asked to estimate based on how many patients they would want to use the DiaSole for under the trial protocol eligibility criteria. They could only select one answer to this question, almost half of the responders were unable to estimate.

Figure 2 shows the frequency of response to the question “What kind of wounds would you use the DiaSole with?”, the podiatrists were allowed to choose more than one option for this question.

Figure 3 shows the frequency of response to the question “Could you estimate the percentage of patients you see that you would want to issue the DiaSole insole to?”.

5. Discussion

5.1. Trial amendments

Due to the difficulties with participant recruitment throughout the trial, a number of significant and non-significant amendments were made and subsequently approved by the MHRA, REC/HCRW bodies. These amendments and their justification are detailed below.

Significant amendment 1 (22/05/2023)

This included clarification and simplification of the participant recruitment process. This was in order to increase attendance at safety follow-up visits, participant retention and allow alignment between participants and research clinicians and the standard care pathway. This amendment changed the protocol to allow certain follow-up visits (weeks 1, 2 and 3) to be completed via video conferencing or via telephone. CRFs were reworked to ensure clean and consistent data capture and reduce missing/errors in data.

Non-significant amendment 1 (05/07/2023)

The PIS, Informed Consent form (ICF) and patient feedback questionnaire were translated into Welsh.

Non-significant amendment 2 (13/09/2023)

The trial deadline was extended to end of March 2024 in order to help with participant recruitment.

Significant amendment 2 (22/11/2023)

Changes were made to patient inclusion and exclusion criteria following feedback from podiatrists who were trying to recruit for the trial. This feedback suggested that patients who could benefit from the insole couldn't be recruited as the selection pool was too small.

Inclusion criteria were updated to include erythema and extravasation at the ulcer/lesion site as appropriate. Sensory neuropathy was no longer deemed an inclusion criteria, this change was due to participant HD_004 being withdrawn. Unfortunately this participant's ulcer had healed once this amendment had been approved.

Additional changes to the eligibility criteria for this amendment included a clarification that more than one ulcer/lesion on the same foot was not a cause for exclusion criteria as this was not clear in previous protocol version. Critical limb ischemia was one of the exclusion criteria, it previously included a mention of moderate to severe peripheral vascular disease which was removed as it was discounting too many patients unnecessarily.

Non-significant amendment 3 (14/03/2024)

The trial deadline was extended to end of September 2024 in order to help with participant recruitment.

Significant amendment 3 (12/08/2024)

The DiaSole insole had minor design changes to the outer rim to ensure that it fitted into a wider range of patient footwear. These small changes were a result of feedback from the research clinicians involved in the trial, in order to help with recruitment because at this point 7 potential participants had been excluded because the DiaSole insole could not fit into their footwear, despite several pairs of footwear being tested in some cases.

5.2. DiaSole workshop discussions

On the 22/05/2024 a workshop was held between the TriTech Institute, research clinicians from HDUHB, Kaydiar LTD. and ConvaTec LTD. This workshop was intended to discuss the difficulties in recruitment throughout the trial period and as an opportunity for the research

clinicians to feedback some of their thoughts on the DiaSole and how it could be more effectively utilised. It was also an opportunity for Kaydiar and ConvaTec to ask questions of the research clinicians and to promote the use of DiaSole.

Feedback from research clinicians indicated that a large majority of the participants that were being screened and who were being considered for screening had Texas grade 0A ulcers or lesions. Research clinicians were more interested in prescribing the DiaSole to potential participants whose ulcers and/or lesions had recently healed as a means to prevent re-occurrence. This was in line with feedback collected from the wider podiatry team (section 4.3.2.) but this was not in alignment with the feedback Kaydiar and ConvaTec had previously obtained (KD, 2022) which suggested the healing of ulcers or lesions would be the main benefit of the DiaSole insoles.

Further to this research clinicians also fed back that they would be able to recruit participants in larger numbers if this could be used for patients who had not yet formed an ulcer or lesion at all but were at risk as means to prevent entirely. But the discussions during the workshop on the 22/05/2024 indicated that this was going outside of the scope of funding ConvaTec had provided. The intention of the DiaSole was it to be included in the wound healing portfolio of projects being sold by ConvaTec.

The research clinicians had previously provided feedback on the cascade of options available to them clinically, where TCCs and air cast offloading boots are clinically proven to be most effective with patients who have Texas grade 1A or more severe ulcers and lesions. This is in line with the podiatry consensus document for offloading (Munro et al., 2021). The rebuttal to this from Kaydiar and ConvaTec was that compliance from patients and clinicians can be low for TCCs (Fife et al., 2014) and that alternative solutions such as felt padding provide poor patient outcomes.

The footwear issue was discussed, and Kaydiar responded with their updated designs for the DiaSole which would allow it to fit into a wider range of footwear more easily. This new design is what was included in the significant amendment approved on 12/08/2024. But unfortunately no suitable participants were found between this date and the trial close out on the 30/09/2024

The discrepancies in the value proposition statement (KD, 2022) were pointed out and more detail was requested from Kaydiar, but none has been provided to date. Discussions for this workshop closed on the assumption from Kaydiar and ConvaTec that HDUHB podiatry have an increased ability to utilise TCC, air cast boots and other more clinically proven offloading options were other NHS institutions would typically struggle and use lesser proven options and that DiaSole may be more valuable in these other institutions.

6. Conclusion

Due to the ongoing difficulties with participant recruitment it has not been possible to come to any meaningful conclusions about the safety and effectiveness of the DiaSole insoles. Of

the 4 participants who were successfully recruited into the trial, 2 had a positive outcome indicating a reduction in ulcer/lesion size and positive feedback from the participants. The other 2 participants were withdrawn from the trial due to new blister or skin formations that were deemed to be a risk for continued use, however the cause of this may not have been solely from the use of DiaSole.

Feedback from HDUHB podiatrists involved in this trial indicated that the DiaSole could see more use in future as a means of completely preventing ulcer or lesion develop in those at risk of diabetic foot ulcers, instead of a means for healing them. However this was not the intention of the funding and steer from the commercial sponsor.

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Appendix 1 – Texas wound classification scale

The University of Texas Staging System for Diabetic Foot Ulcers				
Stage	Grade 0	Grade I	Grade II	Grade III
A	Pre- or post-ulcerative lesion completely epithelialized	Superficial ulcer, not involving tendon capsule or bone	Ulcer penetrating to tendon or capsule	Ulcer penetrating to bone or joint
B	Infection	Infection	Infection	Infection
C	Ischemia	Ischemia	Ischemia	Ischemia
D	Infection & Ischemia	Infection & Ischemia	Infection & Ischemia	Infection & Ischemia
Score: Grade _____ Stage _____				

Appendix 2 – National plantar ulceration off-loading pathway

Appendix 3 – Patient information sheet (PIS)

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET	
Study short title:	Safety evaluation of the DiaSole insole with Diabetic foot ulcers
Version:	V7 22/05/2023
Study Sponsor:	Kaydiar Medical
Name of Chief Investigator:	Mike Mulroy
REC Ref: 22/WA/0342	IRAS Ref: 322107

Please ask us if you would like this Participant Information Sheet translated into Welsh.

1. Invitation and Summary

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you make a decision it is important to explain why the research is being conducted and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with friends, relatives and your GP if you wish. Do not hesitate to ask us if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like additional information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part in the research study.

The DiaSole research study will evaluate the safety and clinical performance of a new insole which has been developed to reduce pressure in key areas of the foot. An insole is a device which is placed inside a shoe, beneath the foot. This insole has been designed with individuals who have Diabetes, with an aim to help reduce the risk of pressure ulcers or lesions in the feet.

2. What is the purpose of the research?

This study insole (DiaSole) has undergone previous research phases which show that it is able to reduce the pressure in at risk areas of the feet and has been safe to use with the small number of individuals that have tried it. This research is to evaluate the clinical performance and safety profile with a larger number of patients who are receiving care for diabetic neuropathy, and who are at risk of developing a pressure lesion or ulcer in the foot or who have a superficial ulcer.

3. Why have I been chosen to take part?

As a patient under the care of the podiatry team within Hywel Dda University Health Board you have been invited to try this new insole instead of one of the other currently used insoles within Hywel Dda University Health Board, so that we can assess its safety and clinical performance and to get your feedback about its use.

4. Do I have to participate in this research?

No, participation in the study is voluntary. It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you decide to take part, you will be given this Participant Information Sheet and you will be asked to sign a consent form that shows us that you have understood what the study involves and that you are happy to take part. You can change your mind and withdraw from the study at any time without giving a reason. Information collected from you up to this point will still be included and evaluated as part of the study. Your withdrawal from the study will not affect your standard care.

5. What will happen if I agree to participate in this research?

If you choose to take part in this study, you will be issued with a pair of DiaSole insoles for use over an 8-week period as part of your offloading care plan provided by the podiatrists. If at any point you withdraw from the study or once your involvement is complete you will resume your standard care which could involve using another standard issue insole or clinical aid prescribed by the podiatry team.

The study involves six study visits over an 8-week period. Where possible the study visits will happen together with your standard podiatry appointments and take place where your usual podiatry appointments are held.

Initial consultation with a podiatrist (week 0 – approximately 1 hour for study purposes). This consultation will include.

- Ensuring using the DiaSole insole fits in with your standard care and to discuss the research with you.
- Completion of the written informed consent form.
- An assessment of your feet including skin condition and sensation levels. Standard care of your feet will also be included as part of this initial consultation.
- Baseline assessment of your health, including history and risk of ulcers and pressure lesion in the feet due to diabetic neuropathy.
- Prescription of DiaSole insoles to fit your footwear which you will wear over the 8-weeks. This may need to be done at another visit, within 5 days of this initial consultation, if the correct size insoles are not available in clinic at this appointment.

Four weekly follow up visits with one of the podiatrists or member of the research team to check progress and to ensure that the insoles are not causing you any issues. (Week 1, 2, 3, & 4 – approximately 30 minutes for study purposes)

Final follow up appointment will take place at the end of week 8 (approximately 45 minutes for study purposes), with the podiatrists. This consultation will include.

- Check your progress and to ensure that the insoles are not causing you any issues
- To ask for your feedback on the insoles and your experience with them.
- Return the study insoles to the podiatrist. Standard care of your feet will also be included as part of this final study visit and one of the other currently used insoles will be issued, if needed.

Photographs may be taken of your feet and ulceration/pressure lesion areas to monitor changes as part of your standard care. With your consent the study team will send copies of any photographs taken during your participation in the study. These photographs will be used for promotional and marketing purposes.

6. What will I have to do?

You will be asked to use the DiaSole insoles in addition to other care instructions from the podiatrist. The DiaSole insoles must only be worn with footwear approved by the podiatrist at time of insole fitting. There will be no other restrictions to your lifestyle or usual activities other than any clinical recommendations from the podiatrist or clinical team.

You will be asked to attend a total of six study visits at one of the podiatry locations within Hywel Dda University Health Board, this will likely be the same location you have previously attended your podiatry appointments.

7. What are the possible benefits associated with me taking part in this research study?

Taking part in this study will help to contribute to advancements in the research and development for the treatment of diabetic foot ulcers/lesions.

8. What are the potential disadvantages and risks of participating in this research?

The risks and disadvantages of using the DiaSole insoles are very similar to the risk present with other insole use as part of pressure offloading care. The most likely risk is skin irritation (such as discolouration or hard skin formation) from poor fitting of the insole or inappropriate footwear.

Other risks that are less likely to occur include:

- Formation of a new foot ulcer or pressure lesion
- Exacerbation to current ulcer or pressure lesion
- Incorrect insole fitting and/or inappropriate footwear which may increase risk of stability and falls.
- Ulceration from rubbing as a result of poor fitting of the insole and/or inappropriate footwear.

All possible risks will be monitored closely during the first four week study visits following prescription of the DiaSole insoles.

The podiatrist team are professionally trained to recognise the early signs of adverse skin events such as skin irritation, pressure transference and pre-ulceration which may develop as a result of taking part in the study.

Taking part in this study will mean you need to attend six study visits, which in some cases may be more than would be needed if you were having standard care. The study visits will take an extra 30 minutes to 1 hours of your time. Where possible these visits will take place alongside your standard podiatry appointments.

The research team is able to offer reimbursement for travel expenses for participants who participate in the study at a flat rate of £20 per participant, which can be claimed for at your final visit (week 8).

9. What will happen if something goes wrong?

If you have any concerns about the study insole, its use or if you think something has gone wrong, please stop using it immediately and contact one of the research team:

Principal Investigator: Mike Mulroy, *Podiatrist, Hywel Dda University Health Board*
Email: mike.mulroy@wales.nhs.uk
Phone: 01554 783197

Research Nurse: Zohra Omar
Email: Zohra.omar@wales.nhs.uk
Phone: 0300 303 6115 - select option 2, TriTech Institute.
Mobile: 07796 381918

Your participation in this research will not change how you access any healthcare that you need. **If at any time you are concerned about the condition of your feet or feel unwell**, please contact your clinical team by your usual route or for non-life-threatening symptoms please contact your GP as you normally would. For any serious or life-threatening medical emergency's please call 999.

In the case of any adverse events, or if you decide that you no longer want to take part in the study, your participation in the study will be concluded and you will return to your usual standard of care.

If you have a concern about any aspect of this study, you should ask to speak to a member of the research team who will do their best to answer your questions.

If you do not get a satisfactory response from them, you are free to contact Kaydiar (the sponsor) of this study via email at david@kaydiar.co.uk or in writing to Gwynnant, Coedffaldau Rd, Neath Port Talbot, SA9 2RL

If you wish to speak to someone who is not part of the study team the normal National Health Service complaints mechanisms are available to you.

www.wales.nhs.uk/ourservices/contactus/nhscomplaints

You can also raise a concern by contacting Patient Support Services at Hywel Dda University Health Board by:

Email: hdbh.patientsupportservices@wales.nhs.uk

Phone: 0300 0200 159

Write a letter to FREEPOST FEEDBACK @ HYWEL DDA

10. What will happen to the results generated by this research?

The results generated by this research will be used to assess the clinical performance and safety profile of the DiaSole insole. The results will also be used by Kaydiar, who are the developers of DiaSole as part of its regulatory approval process. The findings from our study may be published in scientific journals and presented at conferences, all of the results will be fully anonymised and it will not be possible to identify you as a participant

11. Who is organising and funding this evaluation?

This research is being organised and funded by Kaydiar, who are the developers of the DiaSole insole. ConvaTec are also a commercial collaborator with Kaydiar and have provided funding to support this research.

12. How will we use information about you?

The EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the UK Data Protection Act 2018 govern the processing (acquiring, holding, using, etc.) of personal data in the UK.

Kaydiar is the sponsor for this study and are based in the United Kingdom. Kaydiar will use information from you and your medical records and will act as the data controller for this study. This means that the Kaydiar is responsible for looking after your information and using it properly. Kaydiar will not be collecting personal information about you during the study.

All information that is collected about you during this study will be kept strictly confidential. We will need to use information from you and your care relating to your feet for this research study. This information will include your NHS number, name, and site where you received treatment as part of the research. Any information will be coded so you cannot be identified from it. In addition, we will not give any identifiable information to life insurance, private medical insurance companies or any other third parties.

If you provide your consent, your General Practitioner (GP) will be sent a letter, telling them that you are taking part in this study.

Under data protection law, we must provide you with very specific information about what we do with your data and about your rights.

More information on how the sponsor will collect information from you can be requested by contacting the sponsor: David Barton, via email at david@kaydiar.co.uk or in writing to Gwynnant, Coedffaldau Rd, Neath Port Talbot, SA9 2RL

Hywel Dda University Health Board will keep your name, hospital/identification number, gender, age, date of birth, email address and contact details confidential and will not pass this information to Kaydiar.

Hywel Dda University Health Board will use this information as needed, to contact you about the research study, and make sure that relevant information about the study is recorded for your care, and to oversee the quality of the study.

Certain individuals from Kaydiar and regulatory organisations may look at your medical and research records to check the accuracy of the research study. Kaydiar will only receive information without any identifying information. The people who analyse the information will not be able to identify you and will not be able to find out your name, hospital/identification number, gender, age, date of birth, or contact details. In addition, data collected during the study may be looked at by responsible representatives from the sponsor (Kaydiar) for the purposes of monitoring and auditing to ensure that the study is being conducted properly.

All non-anonymised information (i.e., personal data that can be used to identify you; e.g. hospital number, name, date of birth, and contact details including your home address and telephone numbers) will be stored securely for 15 years after the last contact between the research team and yourself according to standard Information Governance (ISO 27001) and NHS Information Governance Toolkit safeguards.

All anonymised information (e.g., your responses to the study questionnaires) will be stored securely for 15 years according to Kaydiar policy. The procedures that will be followed for the collection, storage, protection, retention, and destruction of all information comply with the UK Data Protection Act 2018.

Your rights to access, change or move your information are limited, as we need to manage your information in specific ways in order for the research to be reliable and accurate. If you withdraw from the study, we will keep the information about you that we have already obtained. To safeguard your rights, we will use the minimum personally identifiable information possible.

What are your choices about how your information is used?

- You can stop being part of the study at any time, without giving a reason, but we will keep information about you that we already have.
- We need to manage your records in specific ways for the research to be reliable. This means that we won't be able to let you see or change the data we hold about you.

Where can you find out more about how your information is used?

If you would like to find out more about how and why your information is used, including for research purposes, please visit [NHS Direct Wales](#).

Alternatively, you can check www.hra.nhs.uk/information-about-patients/ or contact the study sponsors Kaydiar via David Barton – david@kaydiar.co.uk Gwynnant, Coedffaldau Rd, Neath Port Talbot, SA9 2RL.

Appendix 4 – Schedule of events for DiaSole trial

Visit	Screening/Baseline Visit 0	F/up Visit 1	F/up Visit 2	F/up Visit 3	F/up Visit 4	End of Study Visit 8
Event/Assessment	Day 0	Day 7	Day 14	Day 21	Day 28	Day 56
Participant eligibility screening	X					
Informed consent	X	X	X	X	X	X
Participant Demographics	X					
Anticoagulant and immunosuppressant medication	X	X	X	X	X	X
Record if Insulin or Non-Insulin dependent diabetic and latest HbA1c result	X					
Lesion Assessment	X	X	X	X	X	X
Lesion grade	X				X	X
Vascular examination	X					
Edinburgh Claudication Questionnaire (ECQ)	X					
Sensory foot examination	X					
Pre-Issue pathway for onward referral (e.g., vascular, orthopaedics, inpatient)	X					
Assessment of feet	X	X	X	X	X	X
Assessment of participant's footwear	X					
Lesion measurements (L x W; D)	X				X	X
DiaSole Insoles fitting & dispensing	X					
DiaSole Insole fitting & assessment	X	X	X	X	X	X
AE / SAE assessment		X	X	X	X	X
Research Podiatrist Assessment of DiaSole insole						X
Participant Questionnaire						X

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